

This is a post-print (final draft post-refereeing). Published in final edited form as:

Rojas-Consuegra, R., Grajales-Nishimura, J.M., Arenillas, I., Arz, J.A., Gilabert, V. y Rosales-Domínguez, M.C. (2026). The K-Pg Río Cangrejo layer in central Cuba: An ejecta-rich backwash deposit over the Caribbean volcanic terrane. *Journal of South American Earth Sciences*, 178, 106092, 1-10,

DOI: 10.1016/j.jsames.2026.106092

Available in:

https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0895981126001446?srnid=5847339&dgcid=SSRN_redirect_SD

1 **The K-Pg Río Cangrejo Layer in Central Cuba: An Ejecta-Rich Backwash Deposit over the**
2 **Caribbean Volcanic Terrane**

3
4 Reinaldo Rojas-Consuegra¹, José Manuel Grajales-Nishimura², Ignacio Arenillas³, José Antonio
5 Arz³, Vicente Gilaberta^{3,4}, María del Carmen Rosales-Domínguez²

6
7 ¹ *Centro de Investigación del Petróleo. Churruca No. 481, Cerro, La Habana, C.P.12000, Cuba.*

8 *E-mail: rojas@ceinpet.cupet.cu; rojasconsuegra@gmail.com*

9 ² *Consultor independiente. C/ Ixcateopan 57, Delegación Benito Juárez, Ciudad de México, C.P.*

10 *03300, México. E-mail: mdcr@yahoo.com*

11 ³ *Departamento de Ciencias de la Tierra e Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Ciencias*
12 *Ambientales de Aragón (IUCA). Universidad de Zaragoza, C/ Pedro Cerbuna 12, Zaragoza, C.P.*
13 *50009, España. E-mail: josearz@unizar.es; ias@unizar.es*

14 ⁴ *Department of Geology, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of the Basque Country*
15 *(UPV/EHU). Bilbao, Spain*

16
17 **Abstract**

18 The Chicxulub meteorite impact produced varied deposits at the Cretaceous-Paleogene (K-Pg)
19 boundary, with effects that enveloped the entire planet. In the Gulf of Mexico and Caribbean
20 region, stratigraphic sections of the K-Pg Complex Clastic Unit (CCU) are being described from
21 different marine environments. This work provides the characterization and formal definition of
22 the Río Cangrejo Layer, a new K-Pg boundary lithostratigraphic unit identified in the Cabaiguán
23 piggy-back basin of central Cuba, which originated upon the Caribbean Volcanic Arc terrane.

24 The new unit is formed by the K-Pg CCU, exhibits several amalgamated layers with marked
25 cross-bedding, and is significantly rich in altered ejecta spherules. Three main intervals were
26 identified in the sequence: a basal grain flow deposit, a middle interval with unidirectional
27 tractive current structures, and an upper level rich in spherules. The foraminiferal association,
28 petrography, and sedimentology of this CCU confirm its origin linked to the Chicxulub impact.
29 The unit records the action of tsunamis and is interpreted as a backwash deposit that eroded the
30 Maastrichtian carbonate platform situated atop the Cretaceous volcanic rocks. The definition of
31 this unit is of special importance for the regional and global stratigraphic correlation of the K-Pg
32 event, particularly in the Caribbean context. The type outcrop, of exceptional scientific value and
33 accessibility, is proposed as a geosite for its conservation, research, and public dissemination
34 concerning the global K-Pg event.

35

36 Keywords: Río Cangrejo Layer, K-Pg, ejecta, central Cuba, Chicxulub impact, backwash deposit,
37 Caribbean Volcanic Terrane.

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40 In Cuba, intensive research on the so-called Cretaceous-Paleogene (K-Pg) boundary deposits has
41 been ongoing for over three decades. Nevertheless, various aspects of interest are still being
42 investigated, and the application of acquired knowledge is crucial for understanding the
43 consequences of a colossal event such as the Chicxulub impact.

44 The Cuban archipelago stands out for its high geodiversity, which is undoubtedly the result of a
45 unique tectono-structural evolution, where paleogeographic diversity has played a fundamental

46 role. Thus, the Cuban geological substrate comprises an amalgam of stratigraphic sequences from
47 a vast, now-vanished region: the western Proto-Caribbean. Here, large geological domains were
48 accreted against the southern margin of North America: the Yucatán platform margin to the west,
49 a Cretaceous intra-oceanic volcanic arc complex and its piggy-back basins, and the Florida-
50 Bahamas continental shelf margin to the north. This diversity is also reflected in a tremendous
51 variability of facies and sequences associated with K-Pg deposits (Rojas-Consuegra and Núñez-
52 Cambra, 2017; Rojas-Consuegra and De Huelbes, 2021).

53 In the western region, associated with the continental margin of the Yucatán block, two key units
54 of this boundary have been clearly identified: the Moncada Formation, which shows
55 stratigraphic-geochronological continuity and a marked iridium anomaly (Tada et al., 2002, 2003;
56 Arenillas et al., 2016; Arz et al., 2022), and the Cacarajícara Formation, characterized by a
57 spectacular basal breccia and a thickness of approximately 800 m, outcropping in the Sierra del
58 Rosario (Kiyokawa et al., 2002; Goto et al., 2008).

59 In contrast, studies on the southern North American paleo-continental margin (Bahamas
60 Platform) have been scarce. However, the Amaro Formation has been related to the K-Pg
61 (Pszczółkowski, 1986, 1999; Iturralde-Vinent, 1992, 1998; Sánchez-Arango, 2011). This unit has
62 a great basal breccia up to 300 m thick, and the presence of latest Maastrichtian planktonic
63 foraminifera and ejecta spherules was confirmed (Fernández-Pérez, 2007).

64 Figure 1

65 In particular, on the substrate of the Cretaceous Volcanic Arc Complex (CVAC) of the country,
66 as part of the Antillean volcanic terrane, several sections exhibit the K-Pg boundary, most
67 notably the Peñalver Formation in western Cuba (Takayama et al., 2000; Tada et al., 2002, 2003;

68 Díaz-Otero et al., 2003; Molina et al., 2002; Goto et al., 2005, 2008; Villegas-Martín and Rojas-
69 Consuegra, 2011; Arenillas et al., 2016; Arz et al., 2022; Rojas-Consuegra et al., 2025a).
70 Furthermore, in central Cuba, a section at Loma Capiro, Santa Clara, corresponding to the
71 northern slope of the CVAC, has been studied in detail (Alegret et al., 2005; Yamamoto et al.,
72 2010; Cobiella-Reguera et al., 2015; Arenillas et al., 2016; Arz et al., 2022).

73 A new type of K-Pg deposit is now recognized in the town of Fomento (Figure 1), where the
74 Complex Clastic Unid (CCU) was accumulated in a piggy-back basin over the Cretaceous
75 Antillean volcanic terrane. This layer is unique in Cuba, given its sedimentological and textural
76 characteristics, its ejecta content, and its importance for local and regional stratigraphic
77 correlation.

78

79 **2. Geological Context**

80 The central Cuba region, as part of the Cuban orogen, is generally constituted, from north to
81 south, by: carbonate sequences of the Florida-Bahamas continental margin, the ophiolitic
82 association in the form of a tectonic *mélange*, the Cretaceous Volcanic Arc Complex and its
83 Cenozoic syn-orogenic and post-orogenic cover, and to the south, the so-called Escambray
84 metamorphic massif of Jurassic-Cretaceous age (Iturralde-Vinent, ed., 2021).

85 **2.1 Cabaiguán Basin**

86 The so-called Cabaiguán Basin extends in an east-west direction, in a relatively narrow strip, as a
87 western extension of the Central Cuba Basin, and is developed on the CVAC terrain (Kantshev et
88 al., 1978; Iturralde-Vinent, ed., 2021).

89 At the base of the regional stratigraphic sequence appear the calc-alkaline series volcanites
90 belonging to the Mataguá Formation (Wassall, 1954) of Aptian-Albian age (Kantshev et al.,
91 1978) (Figure 2).

92 The Upper Cretaceous materials are constituted by varieties of limestones from the Isabel
93 Formation (Truitt and Pardo, 1953) of Maastrichtian age, which are bioconstructed platform
94 carbonates, with rudists, gastropods, echinoderms, worms, large orbitoidal benthic foraminifera,
95 corals, and other marine organisms. "Peri-reefal" bioclastics and transported slope facies also
96 appear (Rojas-Consuegra, 2005; Meléndez et al., 2013). These carbonates transition laterally and
97 vertically, with interdigitations, into facies of siltstone, shale, marl, and fine sandstone, reddish to
98 purple in color of Maastrichtian age (Popov et al., 1978); lithologies also referred to this unit,
99 representing the deeper distal platform (Figure 2).

100 Figure 2.

101 The UCC, here defined as the "Río Cangrejo Layer", lies over the Cretaceous units through an
102 erosive surface, which in the outcrop studied in detail at Fomento, affects the reddish sandstone
103 and shale of the lower part of the Isabel Fm. Above it, the marls and shales of the Fomento Fm.
104 (Truitt and Pardo, 1953b), of Paleocene – early Eocene age, are arranged. These materials are
105 generally located through an erosive discontinuity over the Cretaceous platform, except at very
106 specific points where, between both formations, the ejecta-rich unit is preserved (Figure 3).

107 Figure 3.

108 Over the Fomento Fm. in part of the basin appears the Jucillo Fm. (Truitt and Pardo, 1953,
109 redefined by Kantshev et al. 1978), consisting of breccias with a basal cement and angular clasts
110 of diabases, andesites, tuffs, acid effusives, epidote, altered and silicified rocks, limestones, and

111 sandstones. The breccia cement is scarce or non-existent, and although it lacks fossils, it contains
112 limestone clasts from the Maastrichtian (Kantshev et al. 1978). Based on its stratigraphic
113 position, over the Paleocene Fomento Fm. and below the early Eocene - middle Eocene Zaza
114 Fm., it is assigned an early Eocene age (Iturralde-Vinent, ed., 2021).

115 Covering the previous units, with significant distribution, is the Zaza Fm. (Thiadens, 1937),
116 composed of a finely stratified sequence of sandstone, polymictic conglomerate, and grey-
117 greenish siltstone, alternating with thin layers of tuffite and zeolitized tuff of early-middle Eocene
118 age (Figure 3).

119 The simplified geological scheme (Figure 1) is based on the 1:100,000 Map (IGP, 2010). The
120 nomenclature, age, and thicknesses of the lithostratigraphic units are according to the
121 Stratigraphic Lexicon of Cuba (IGP, 2024).

122

123 **3. Materials and Methods**

124 This study is based on multidisciplinary research conducted over several years in the Fomento
125 area. The methodology integrated a comprehensive bibliographic review, detailed field
126 observations, and subsequent laboratory analyses to characterize the K-Pg boundary section.

127 The research focuses on a key outcrop near Fomento town, south-central Cuba, located southeast
128 of the previously studied K-Pg section at Loma Capiro, Santa Clara (Alegret et al., 2005;
129 Yamamoto et al., 2010). The studied section, which exposes the Cretaceous-Paleogene transition,
130 was cleaned and documented in an excavated trench measuring approximately 25 m in length and
131 up to 3 m in height. Multiple field campaigns were conducted for detailed lithological
132 descriptions, photographic documentation, and structural measurement (N165°-175°E; dip:

133 25°N). Systematic sampling was performed across the complete stratigraphic sequence, which
134 comprises reddish marls and siltstones of the Maastrichtian Isabel Formation at the base, a 2-2.5
135 m thick clastic unit of the Cretaceous-Paleogene boundary in the middle, and whitish to grey
136 calcareous marls of the Lower Paleocene at the top. A detailed lithostratigraphic column of this
137 sequence was elaborated (Figure 4).

138 Figure 4

139 Comprehensive laboratory analyses were performed on the collected samples. A total of 2.5 m of
140 the Isabel Formation was sampled at different intervals (20 cm, 10 cm, and 3 cm), 13 samples
141 were taken from the clastic unit for thin sections, granulometry, and washing, and 1.5 m of the
142 Paleocene deposits were sampled at 2 cm intervals. Analytical techniques included: (1)
143 micropaleontological analysis of 25 siltstone and marl samples processed using H₂O₂ levigation
144 to concentrate planktonic foraminifera; (2) petrographic study of 13 thin sections for detailed
145 microscopic examination; (3) textural and compositional analysis of four samples from below the
146 clastic unit; (4) qualitative mineralogical analysis via EDS spectroscopy on selected samples; and
147 (5) granulometric analyses to characterize sediment texture. Planktonic foraminiferal zonation
148 followed the schemes of Arz & Molina (2002) and Berggren & Pearson (2005) for
149 biochronological assessment. The clastic unit is characterized by a strongly heterometric grain
150 size distribution with clay-sized particles and clastic components (mainly lithics and bioclasts) up
151 to 2.2 mm in diameter, displaying a matrix-supported texture where the clay component forms
152 the rock matrix.

153 This study is based on multidisciplinary research conducted over several years in the Fomento
154 area. The methodology integrated bibliographic review, field observations, and laboratory
155 analyses to characterize the K-Pg boundary section.

156

157 **4. Results**

158 The studies carried out in the Fomento section and its surroundings have provided new data that
159 contribute to a better understanding of the stratigraphy of the region. The most valuable findings
160 on the facies of the Isabel Fm., the detailed study of the UCC of the Río Cangrejo Layer, and
161 contributions to the fossil record of the Fomento Fm. are provided below.

162 **4.1 Isabel Formation**

163 In the study area, the Isabel Formation comprises two different facies assemblages: neritic
164 platform carbonates and calcareous sandy-clayey facies of the outer platform to basin.

165 a) Biogenic, biotrital and sandy limestones: This facies was deposited in a shallow carbonate
166 water environment, with variable energy conditions, and with little content of components
167 derived from the erosion of volcanic arc rocks.

168 b) Sandy marl and siltstone: These facies of the Isabel formation were studied in detail. The
169 identified components and their estimated proportions below the clastic unit are: Clay (35-50%);
170 Bioclasts (20-36%); Lithic fragments (3-10%); Volcaniclastic material (7-20%); Minor or
171 accessory components (<5%).

172 **4.2 Río Cangrejo Layer**

173 The outcrop of the UCC consists of three main levels with a total thickness of between 2 and 2.5
174 meters. The base of the UC is a very marked erosive surface on the red shale of the lower part of
175 the Maastrichtian Isabel Fm. Its top is another smoother erosional surface, on which the whitish
176 marls and shales of the Paleocene Fomento Fm. are arranged.

177 The UCC of the K-Pg of Fomento is described here for the first time so that it is defined as a new
178 formal unit, which is called the Río Cangrejo Layer.

179 Origin of the name: Due to the Cangrejos River, which crosses east of the town of Fomento,
180 Sancti Spíritus province, central Cuba.

181 Type area: The type area of the new unit is located to the E and NE of the aforementioned town.

182 Holostratotype: The section located about 100 m from the east bank of the Cangrejos River is
183 designated as the holostratotype (22° 6' 33" N, -79° 42' 38" W).

184 Lectostratotype: The outcrop in the Las Pozas neighborhood is defined as the lectostratotype (21°
185 56' 27.38" N, -79° 37' 20.24" W). The presence of the spherule-rich layer at this locality has
186 recently been confirmed (Rojas-Consuegra et al., 2025b).

187 Geographical distribution: The geographical distribution of this unit is given by its development
188 in the surroundings of the town of Fomento.

189 Lithology: The main lithologies that make up the so-called Río Cangrejo Layer are
190 microconglomerate to calcirudite in parts with lutitic matrix, calcarenite and siltstone, marked by
191 distinctive cross-bedding, with fragments of rudist mollusk shells, gastropods and other fossil
192 invertebrates (Figure 5). It is characterized by a significant abundance of weathered, carbonated
193 and clayish spherules, components of the Chicxulub impact ejecta.

194 Figure 5

195 In the stratigraphic section of the UCC, three well-differentiated levels appear (Meléndez et al.,
196 2013), which are (Figures 3-4): a) Coarse grain calcarenite basal level up to 1 m thick; b) The

197 second crossed beading calcarenites level has a thickness between 50 and 80 cm; and c) The third
198 and last level consists of 40 - 50 cm of calcarenites with positive grain selection.

199 **4.2.1 Ejecta materials**

200 The spherules are generally very weathered, their appearance is varied, they tend to be spherical,
201 globular and even drop-shaped. They are of various sizes, from about a centimeter and in some
202 cases larger, to smaller than a millimeter (microspherules). In some spherules, a darker inner core
203 with a white coating is observed (Belza et al., 2015) (Figure 6). Although some partial ordering in
204 the granulometry is noted, grain changes prevail at different levels, with variations in lamination.

205 Figure 6

206 Selected spherules were analyzed using electron microscopy coupled with energy-dispersive X-
207 ray spectroscopy (EDS). The resulting compositional data are qualitative. The samples contain
208 basement fragments (quartz schist), quartz grains, and a matrix consisting of a mixture of
209 carbonate lithics, bioclasts, clay material, and quartz grains. Notably, shocked quartz grains
210 exhibiting planar deformation features (PDFs) were identified. The spherules themselves show
211 varied compositions: some are composed of calcite and clay; others consist of calcite with an
212 outer rim of clay; and some contain calcite with darker crystalline phases, likely feldspar or
213 zeolite. Additionally, spherules composed of calcite with barium-bearing zeolite, potentially
214 harmotome or phillipsite, were observed (Figure 7).

215 Figure 7

216 **4.3 Fomento Formation**

217 As previously documented, the silts and marls overlying the Complex Clastic Unit (K-Pg)
218 contain Danian planktonic foraminifera (Arz et al., 2011; Meléndez et al., 2013). This study
219 provides a more in-depth analysis of these deposits.

220 4.3.1 Planktic foraminiferal biostratigraphy in the Fomento section

221 *Maastrichtian interval (Isabel Formation)*

222 Forty-nine species belonging to eighteen genera have been identified in the last 2.5 meters of the
223 Maastrichtian in the Fomento section (Figure 8). The identified Maastrichtian genera, and the
224 abbreviations used in Figure 8, are the following: *Guembelitra* (*Gb.*), *Planoheterohelix* (*Phx.*;
225 *Heterohelix* s.l.), *Laeviheterohelix* (*Lhx.*; *Heterohelix* s.l.); *Pseudotextularia* (*Pt.*),
226 *Pseudoguembelina* (*P.*), *Gublerina* (*Gu.*), *Planoglobulina* (*Pl.*), *Racemiguembelina* (*R.*),
227 *Planohedbergella* (*Ph.*; *Globigerinelloides* s.l.), *Muricohedbergella* (*Mh.*; *Hedbergella* s.l.),
228 *Rugoglobigerina* (*R.*), *Archaeoglobigerina* (*A.*), *Globotruncanella* (*Glla.*), *Abathomphalus* (*Ab.*),
229 *Gansserina* (*Gs.*), *Globotruncana* (*Gna.*), *Globotruncanita* (*Gta.*), *Contusotruncana* (*C.*).

230 Figura 8

231 These species and genera belong to polytaxic assemblages typical of the tropical-subtropical
232 Maastrichtian. These assemblages include *Pseudoguembelina hariaensis* and *Abathomphalus*
233 *mayaroensis*, indicating that they belong to the *P. hariaensis* Subzone of Arz and Molina (2002)
234 or Biozone CF-2 of Li and Keller (1998). The base of the *P. hariaensis* Subzone, defined with the
235 lowest occurrence datum (LOD) of the homonymous species, has been dated at ~970 kyr before
236 the K/Pg boundary (Coccioni and Premoli-Silva, 2015; Gradstein et al., 2020).

237 The species *Plummerita hantkeninoides*, whose LOD marks the base of the homonymous
238 subzone of Arz and Molina (2002) or Biozone CF1 of Li and Keller (1998), has not been

239 identified, suggesting that the last 100 kyr of the Maastrichtian are absent in Fomento (Gilabert et
240 al., 2022). Furthermore, the presence of *Gansserina gansseri* in the studied Maastrichtian interval
241 provides a key data point. Its highest occurrence datum (HOD) is dated at ~480 kyr before the
242 K/Pg boundary (Radmacher et al., 2025). This suggests that the Maastrichtian of the Fomento
243 section spans an interval situated between ~970 and ~480 kyr before the K/Pg boundary.
244 Consequently, there is a hiatus affecting the uppermost Maastrichtian of >550 kyr.

245 *Danian interval (Fomento Formation)*

246 Thirty-five species belonging to ten genera have been identified in the last 1.5 meters of the
247 Danian in the Fomento section. The identified Danian genera, and the abbreviations used in
248 Figure 8, are the following: *Chiloguembelitra* (Chg.), *Woodringina* (W.), *Chiloguembelina*
249 (*Ch.*), *Globoconusa* (*Gc.*), *Eoglobigerina* (*E.*), *Parasubbotina* (*P.*), *Globanomalina* (*G.*),
250 *Subbotina* (*S.*), *Praemurica* (*Pr.*), *Acarinina* (*A.*).

251 These assemblages include *Globanomalina compressa*, indicating that they belong to the Biozone
252 P1c of Wade et al. (2011). The base of the Biozone P1c, defined with the LOD of *G. compressa*,
253 has been dated at ~550 kyr after the K/Pg boundary (Gilabert et al., 2022). The Biozone P1d of
254 Smit (1982) and Smit & Romein (1985) has also been identified in the last 60 cm of the studied
255 Danian. The base of this biozone, defined with the LOD of *Acarinina trinidadensis*, has been
256 dated at ~2100 kyr after the K/Pg boundary (Metsana-Oussaid et al., 2019; re-calibrated using the
257 GTS2020 by Gradstein et al., 2020). These data suggest that the studied Danian interval is very
258 condensed, with a sedimentation rate <0.08 cm/kyr, and there is a hiatus affecting the lowermost
259 Danian of >550 kyr.

260 Nevertheless, the thin cm-thick clayey layer that overlies the Capa Río Cangrejo contains mixed
261 assemblages of the Biozones P α , P1a, P1b and P1c of Wade et al. (2011), with a total of forty-
262 one Danian species, including *Parvularugoglobigerina longiapertura*, *Parvularugoglobigerina*
263 *eugubina*, *Parasubbotina pseudobulloides*, *Subbotina triloculinoides* and *Globanomalina*
264 *compressa*. This layer is a condensed level (hardground) and, in addition to most of those
265 mentioned above, includes the following other genera (with the abbreviations used in Fig. 8):
266 *Guembeltria* (Gb.), *Trochoguembeltria* (T.), *Parvularugoglobigerina* (Pv.), and
267 *Palaeoglobigerina* (Pg.).

268

269 **5. Discussion**

270 The geological units Isabel Formation (late Maastrichtian) and the newly named Río Cangrejo
271 Layer, exhibit a diversity of sedimentary facies that reflect particular processes associated with
272 the Chicxulub meteoritic impact in Yucatán.

273 **5.1 Interpretation of Isabel Formation facies**

274 The basal marl and silt, relative to the erosional surface covered by the UCC, belong to the
275 *Pseudoguembelina hariaensis* subzone (upper Maastrichtian).

276 At this base of the section, effects of the seismicity associated with the Chicxulub impact have
277 recently been identified (Bermúdez et al., 2024). Here, these rocks of the Isabel Fm. exhibit a
278 very particular system of parallel fractures, with block displacement in that pre-impact substrate
279 (seismites *s.l.*), whose fragments were included in the lower subunit of the spherule-rich deposit
280 (Figures 6 y 7).

281 In general, the Isabel Fm. in the area contains shallow carbonate platform facies, with abundant
282 organisms in situ, more open water facies and other clastic facies with different textures,
283 including breccias and slope collapse deposits rich in resedimented corals, rudists, gastropods,
284 equinoids and other macrofossils. Among the latter, there are accumulations that may also
285 respond to processes related to the K-Pg boundary in the region, which remains to be studied in
286 detail.

287 **5.2 Interpretation of the UCC**

288 It is pertinent to note that the CCU of the Río Cangrejo Layer appears to have been described by
289 Kantchev et al. (1978, p. 792). The spherule layer was described as "whitish to greenish, clayey
290 and zeolitized tuffs. The thickness of these intercalations is 20-30 cm up to 2-3 m"; according to
291 the new content they assigned to the Fomento Formation.

292 The CCU of Río Cangrejo, according to its general features and thickness, is distinguished from
293 previously described deposits by its specific characteristics.

294 • The textural characteristics, composition, grain distribution, and sedimentary structures present
295 in the first level (1) of the CCU are interpreted as a grain flow deposit caused by the direct impact
296 of the tsunami, dragging a dense flow with fragments of the Maastrichtian carbonate platform.

297 • The second level (2) is characterized by an amalgamated set of erosive bodies with cross-
298 bedding.

299 • Finally, the third calcarenitic level (3) with grain selection must correspond to a final grain flow
300 transport event.

301 In summary, the K-Pg boundary outcrops in western Cuba show a great variety in the type and
302 thickness of sediments. The Cacarajícara Formation has a thickness of more than 750 m, the

303 Moncada outcrop of this calcareous unit does not exceed 2 m in thickness, and the Peñalver
304 Formation on the terrain of the extinct Cretaceous volcanic arc reaches 180 m in thickness. At
305 Loma Capiro, in Santa Clara city, about 80 km north of Fomento town, a CCU rich in ejecta, with
306 a 9 m thickness, corresponding to the volcanic arc slope, was described. However, the Río
307 Cangrejo Layer, with a thickness of a few meters, stands out for its unique characteristics among
308 the K-Pg deposits on the volcanic terrane in Cuba.

309 Furthermore, the correlation of this new unit between the Cabaiguán Basin and the Central Basin
310 to the east is demonstrated by the discovery of identical spherule intervals in deep wells from the
311 hydrocarbon-producing Pina area (Gonzales-Leyva et al., 2025).

312 In the Caribbean region, the Río Cangrejo Layer is comparable with isochronous deposits
313 recognized in Haiti (Maurrasse et al., 1991; Izett et al., 1991; Arenillas et al., 2016; Arz et al.
314 2022), as well as with numerous sites in the Gulf of Mexico, the Americas (Arenillas et al., in this
315 volume) and the rest of the world where ejecta is present.

316

317 **6. Conclusions**

318 The Río Cangrejo Layer is formally defined as a new lithostratigraphic unit for the Cretaceous-
319 Paleogene (K-Pg) boundary. This unit constitutes a guide stratum for the Cabaiguán basin, lying
320 discordantly over the Isabel Formation (Maastrichtian) and covered by the Fomento Formation
321 (Paleocene-Early Eocene).

322 The foraminiferal associations, petrography, sedimentology and ejecta of the Río Cangrejo Layer
323 confirm its origin linked to the Chicxulub impact. The unit records the action of tsunamis and is
324 interpreted as a backwash deposit that eroded the Maastrichtian carbonate platform.

325 The depositional mechanism involved multiple high-energy flow events. The vertical succession
326 of facies - from dense grain flows (Level 1) to unidirectional tractive currents (Level 2) and a
327 final flow with a high concentration of spherules (Level 3) - documents the evolution of
328 hydrodynamic energy after the impact.

329 Evidence of impact-induced seismicity (seismites) is identified at the top of the Isabel Formation,
330 proving the violence of the event and its role in the fragmentation of the substrate, whose clasts
331 were incorporated into the base of the UCC.

332 The Río Cangrejo Layer allows for precise correlation at both regional (with K-Pg units in Cuba
333 and the Caribbean) and global (with the Chicxulub event) scales. Its stratigraphic position
334 unequivocally marks the base of the Cenozoic in the region.

335 Due to its exceptional ejecta content, accessibility, and scientific value, the type outcrop of the
336 Río Cangrejo Layer is proposed as a geosite of national and international relevance, with
337 potential for research, education, and geotourism.

338

339 **Acknowledgments**

340 This research was subsidized by the Department of Education and Science of the Autonomous
341 Community of Aragon (Group E05) and by projects CGL2011-22912 and CGL2011-23077 from
342 the Ministry of Education and Science of Spain (co-financed by the European Regional
343 Development Fund). The National Museum of Natural History of Cuba (MNHNC), belonging to
344 the Environment Agency of the Ministry of Science, Technology and Environment (Citma), and
345 the Oil Research Center of the Ministry of Energy and Mines provided fundamental support for
346 the fieldwork, research, and preparation of this manuscript.

347 The lead author (RRC) wishes to especially thank Dr. Gordon Osinski (Departments of Earth
348 Sciences, Physics & Astronomy, University of Western Ontario, Canada) and colleague Jeffrey
349 de Fourestier, FMinSoc (IMA CNMNC Subcommittee on Unnamed Minerals), for their
350 invaluable assistance in the analysis and interpretation of the mineralogical composition of the
351 spherules.

352 We are very grateful to colleagues Dr. Osmany Ceballo-Melendres and Ing. Roberty Hernández
353 Valdés for their essential collaboration in the field campaigns in central Cuba. We extend our
354 gratitude to all colleagues and friends who participated in this effort. We also thank the logistical
355 and institutional support of the Citma Regulatory Office in the province of Sancti Spíritus.

356 A special remembrance and honor to our dear friend and colleague Professor Alfonso Meléndez
357 Hevia (R.I.P.), who participated with cheerful enthusiasm in our studies, and whose ideas and
358 writings are also contained in this work.

359 This research is part of the project "Complex clastic unit of the Cretaceous-Paleogene boundary
360 in Cuba and its relationship with geological evolution", of the I+D sectoral program of the
361 Instituto de Geología y Paleontología/Servicio Geológico de Cuba (IGP/SGC, Ministerio de
362 Energía y Minas).

363 We acknowledge the use of the DeepSeek AI for language editing, grammatical review, and
364 partial translation of the article.

365

366 **References**

367 Alegret, L., Arenillas, I., Arz, J. A., Díaz, C., Grajales-Nishimura, M., Meléndez, A., Molina, E.,
368 Rojas, R., & Soria, A. R. (2005). Cretaceous-Paleogene boundary deposits at Loma Capiro:

369 Evidence for the Chicxulub impact. *Geology*, 33(9), 721–724.
370 <https://doi.org/10.1130/G21563.1>

371 Arenillas, I., Arz, J. A., Grajales-Nishimura, J. M., & Rojas, R. (2016). The Chicxulub impact is
372 synchronous with the planktonic foraminifera mass extinction at the Cretaceous/Paleogene
373 boundary: New evidence from the Moncada section, Cuba. *Geologica Acta*, 14(1), 35–51.

374 Arz, J. A., & Molina, E. (2002). Bioestratigrafía y cronoestratigrafía con foraminíferos
375 planctónicos del Campaniense superior y Maastrichtiense de latitudes subtropicales y templadas
376 (España, Francia y Tunicia). *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen*,
377 224, 161–195.

378 Arz, J. A., Arenillas, I., Grajales-Nishimura, J. M., Liesa, C. L., Soria, A. R., Rojas, R., Calmus,
379 T., & Gilabert, V. (2022). No evidence of multiple asteroid impacts near the Gulf of México,
380 based on Cretaceous-Paleogene planktic foraminiferal biochronology. *Geological Society of*
381 *America Special Paper 557*. [https://doi.org/10.1130/2022.2557\(20\)](https://doi.org/10.1130/2022.2557(20))

382 Belza, J., Goderis, S., Smit, J., Vanhaecke, F., Baert, K., Terryn, H., & Claeys, P. (2015). High
383 spatial resolution geochemistry and textural characteristics of ‘microtektite’ glass spherules in
384 proximal Cretaceous–Paleogene sections: Insights into glass alteration pattern and precursor
385 melt lithologies. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 152, 1–38.
386 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2014.12.013>

387 Berggren, W. A., & Pearson, P. N. (2005). A revised tropical to subtropical Paleogene planktonic
388 foraminiferal zonation. *Journal of Foraminiferal Research*, 35(4), 279–298.
389 <https://doi.org/10.2113/35.4.279>

390 Bermudez, H. D., Bolivar, L., Martini, M., Vega, F. J., Arenillas, I., Arz, J. A., Gilabert, V.,
391 Phillips, G., Bermudez, D., Garb, M., Vega-Sandoval, F. A., Rojas-Consuegra, R., Nuñez-
392 Cambra, K. E., Berry, K., Korbar, T., Gomez, C., & Cui, Y. (2024). El megaterremoto de

393 Chicxulub: evidencia en el registro geológico de Europa occidental y las Américas [The
394 Chicxulub megathrust earthquake: Evidence in the geological record of Western Europe and the
395 Americas]. *Geological Society of America Abstracts with Programs*, 56(5).
396 <https://doi.org/10.1130/abs/2024AM-401171>

397 Cobiella-Reguera, J. L., Cruz, E. M., Blanco, S., Pérez, L., Gil-González, S., & Pedraza, Y. (2015).
398 Cretaceous/Paleogene boundary deposits and paleogeography in western and central Cuba.
399 *Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Geológicas*, 32(1), 156–176.

400 Coccioni, R., & Premoli Silva, I. (2015). Revised Upper Albian–Maastrichtian planktonic
401 foraminiferal biostratigraphy and magneto-stratigraphy of the classical Tethyan Gubbio section
402 (Italy). *Newsletters on Stratigraphy*, 48(1), 47–90. <https://doi.org/10.1127/nos/2015/0055>

403 Díaz-Otero, C., Arz, J. A., Arenillas, I., Molina, E., & Corona, C. (2003). Nuevas consideraciones
404 sobre la edad de la Formación Vía Blanca [New considerations on the age of the Vía Blanca
405 Formation]. In V Congreso Cubano de Geología y Minería, *Memorias Geomin 2003*.

406 Fernández-Pérez, J. (2007). Acerca del límite Cretácico-Terciario (K/T) en pozos de la franja norte
407 cubana de crudos pesados [On the Cretaceous-Tertiary (K/T) boundary in wells of the Cuban
408 heavy oil belt]. In II Convención Cubana de Ciencias de la Tierra, Instituto de Geología y
409 Paleontología de Cuba.

410 Gilabert, V., Batenburg, S. J., Arenillas, I., & Arz, J. A. (2022). Contribution of orbital forcing and
411 Deccan volcanism to global climatic and biotic changes across the KP/B at Zumaia, Spain.
412 *Geology*, 50(1), 21–25. <https://doi.org/10.1130/G49214.1>

413 González-Leyva, L., Banzo Morales, S., Torres La Rosa, M., & Rojas Consuegra, R. (2025).
414 Hallazgo de material de eyecta en los pozos Pina 300 y 305, provincia Ciego de Ávila [Finding
415 of eyecta material in the Pina 300 and 305 wells, Ciego de Ávila province]. In *Fórum de Ciencia
416 y Técnica, Ceinpet*.

417 Goto, K., Tada, R., Tajika, E., Iturralde-Vinent, M. A., Matsui, T., Yamamoto, S., Nakano, Y., Oji,
418 T., Kiyokawa, S., Garcia, D., Otero, C., & Rojas, R. (2008). Lateral lithological and
419 compositional variations of the Cretaceous/Tertiary deep-sea tsunami deposit in northwestern
420 Cuba. *Cretaceous Research*, 29(2), 217–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cretres.2007.05.001>

421 Gradstein, F. M., Ogg, J. G., Schmitz, M. D., & Ogg, G. M. (2020). *The geologic time scale 2020*.
422 Elsevier.

423 Hildebrand, A. R., & Boynton, W. V. (1990). Proximal Cretaceous–Tertiary boundary impact
424 deposits in the Caribbean. *Science*, 248(4957), 843–847.
425 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.248.4957.843>

426 Instituto de Geología y Paleontología (IGP). (2024). *Léxico Estratigráfico de Cuba [Stratigraphic*
427 *Lexicon of Cuba]*. Instituto de Geología y Paleontología / Servicio Geológico de Cuba
428 (MINEM).

429 Iturralde-Vinent, M. A. (Ed.). (2021). *Geología de Cuba y del Caribe: Compendio [Geology of*
430 *Cuba and the Caribbean: Compendium]*. Editorial CITMATEL.

431 Iturralde-Vinent, M. A. (1992). A short note on the Cuban late Maastrichtian megaturbidite (an
432 impact-derived deposit?). *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 109(1–2), 225–228.
433 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0012-821X\(92\)90085-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0012-821X(92)90085-4)

434 Iturralde-Vinent, M. A. (1998). Sinopsis de la constitución geológica de Cuba [Synopsis of the
435 geological constitution of Cuba]. *Acta Geológica Hispánica*, 33(1–4), 9–56.

436 Izett, G. A., Dalrymple, G. B., & Snee, L. W. (1991). $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ Age of Cretaceous-Tertiary
437 Boundary Tektites from Haiti. *Science*, 252(5012), 1539–1542.
438 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.252.5012.1539>

439 Kantshev, I., Boyanov, I., Popov, N., Cabrera, R., Goranov, A., Iolkicev, I., Kanszirski, M., &
440 Stancheva, M. (1978). *Geología de la provincia de Las Villas. Resultado de las investigaciones*

441 y levantamiento geológico a escala 1: 250 000 [Geology of the Las Villas province. Result of
442 research and geological survey at 1:250,000 scale]. Ministerio de Energía y Minas, Oficina
443 Nacional de Recursos Minerales.

444 Kiyokawa, S., Tada, R., Iturralde-Vinent, M. A., Matsui, T., Tajika, E., Yamamoto, S., Oji, T.,
445 Nakano, Y., Goto, K., Takayama, H., Garcia, D., Díaz, C., & Rojas, R. (2002). Cretaceous-
446 Tertiary boundary sequence in the Cacarajicara Formation, western Cuba: An impact-related
447 high-energy, gravity flow deposit. In C. Koeberl & K. G. MacLeod (Eds.), *Catastrophic events
448 and mass extinctions: Impacts and beyond* (Vol. 356, pp. 125–144). Geological Society of
449 America Special Paper.

450 Li, L., & Keller, G. (1998). Diversification and extinction in Campanian-Maastrichtian planktic
451 foraminifera of northwestern Tunisia. *Eclogae Geologicae Helvetiae*, 91(1), 75–102.

452 Maurrasse, F. J.-M. R., & Sen, G. (1991). Impacts, tsunamis, and the Haitian Cretaceous–Tertiary
453 boundary layer. *Science*, 252(5013), 1690–1693.
454 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.252.5013.1690>

455 Meléndez Hevia, A., Arz, J. A., Arenillas, I., Menéndez, L., Rojas-Consuegra, R., Grajales-
456 Nishimura, J. M., Rosales, M. C., & Ceballo, O. (2013). Depósitos de grainflow
457 unidireccionales en una unidad clástica relacionada con el impacto de Chicxulub en Fomento,
458 provincia de Sancti Spíritus (Cuba) [Unidirectional grainflow deposits in a clastic unit related
459 to the Chicxulub impact in Fomento, Sancti Spíritus province (Cuba)]. In V Convención Cubana
460 de Ciencias de la Tierra. Sociedad Cubana de Geología.

461 Metsana-Oussaid, F., Belhai, D., Arenillas, I., Arz, J. A., & Gilabert, V. (2019). New sections of
462 the Cretaceous-Paleogene transition in the southwestern Tethys (Médéa, northern Algeria):
463 planktic foraminiferal biostratigraphy and biochronology. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 12,
464 217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-019-4402-4>

465 Molina, E., Arenillas, I., Arz, J. A., Díaz, C., García, D., Meléndez, A., & Rojas, R. (2002).
466 Micropaleontología, Cronoestratigrafía y Sedimentología del límite Cretácico/Terciario en el
467 NO de Cuba [Micropaleontology, Chronostratigraphy and Sedimentology of the
468 Cretaceous/Tertiary boundary in NW Cuba]. *Geogaceta*, 32, 281–284.

469 Popov, N., & Kantchev, I. (1978). In I. Kantchev et al., *Geología de la provincia de Las Villas.*
470 *Resultados de las investigaciones geológicas y levantamiento geológico a escala 1:250 000,*
471 *realizado durante el período 1969-1975, Brigada Cubano-Búlgara* [Geology of the Las Villas
472 province. Results of geological research and survey at 1:250,000 scale, carried out during 1969-
473 1975, Cuban-Bulgarian Brigade]. Instituto de Geología y Paleontología, Academia de Ciencias
474 de Cuba.

475 Pszczółkowski, A. (1986). Megacapas del Maastrichtiano en Cuba occidental y central
476 [Maastrichtian megabeds in western and central Cuba]. *Bulletin of the Polish Academy of*
477 *Sciences, Earth Sciences*, 34(1), 81–94.

478 Pszczółkowski, A. (1999). The exposed passive margin of North America in western Cuba. In
479 *Sedimentary basins of the world* (Vol. 4, pp. 93–121). Elsevier.

480 Radmacher, W., Niezgodzki, I., Gilabert, V., Knorr, G., Buchs, D., Arz, J. A., Arenillas, I., Pearce,
481 M. A., Tyszka, J., Mikołajczak, M., Vasquez, O. J., Ashckenazi-Polivoda, S., Abramovich, S.,
482 Niechwedowicz, M., & Mangerud, G. (2025). 'Fresh end' of the Mesozoic? *Nature*
483 *Communications*, 16, 7238. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-62189-9>

484 Rojas-Consuegra, R. (2005). Estratigrafía, Tafonomía y Paleoecología de los Rudistas (Moluscos
485 Cretácicos) en el territorio cubano [Stratigraphy, Taphonomy and Paleoecology of Rudists
486 (Cretaceous Mollusks) in the Cuban territory]. In *I Convención sobre Ciencias de La Tierra,*
487 *Centro Nacional de Información Geológica.*

488 Rojas-Consuegra, R., & De Huelbes Alonso, J. (2021). Supergrupo cronoestratigráfico del evento
489 K-Pg (Daniano basal): una propuesta para el Léxico Estratigráfico de Cuba
490 [Chronostratigraphic Supergroup of the K-Pg event (basal Danian): a proposal for the
491 Stratigraphic Lexicon of Cuba]. In XIV Convención sobre Ciencias de La Tierra.

492 Rojas-Consuegra, R., Samón Isaac, G., & Nuñez Cambra, K. E. (2025a). Extraordinario depósito
493 clástico-caótico en la Formación Peñalver del límite Cretácico – Paleógeno en el Mariel, Cuba
494 occidental [Extraordinary clastic-chaotic deposit in the Peñalver Formation of the Cretaceous-
495 Paleogene boundary in Mariel, western Cuba]. *Geociencias UO*, 15(1), 14–31.

496 Rojas-Consuegra, R., Rochette, P., Ceballo Meléndez, O., & Hernández Valdés, R. F. (2025b).
497 Depósito esferulítico del límite K-Pg en Las Pozas, provincia Sancti Spíritus, Cuba central
498 [Spherulitic deposit of the K-Pg boundary in Las Pozas, Sancti Spíritus province, central Cuba].
499 En XI Convención de Geociencias de la Tierra.

500 Rojas-Consuegra, R., & Núñez Cambra, K. (2017). Guía para la excursión al límite K-Pg en Cuba
501 occidental [Guide for the excursion to the K-Pg boundary in western Cuba]. In VII Convención
502 de Ciencias de La Tierra, Sociedad Cubana de Geología.

503 Sánchez Arango, J. R. (2011). Una alternativa no catastrófica en la génesis de las clastitas del K/T
504 en Cuba central y occidental. Importancia en la exploración de hidrocarburos costa afuera [A
505 non-catastrophic alternative in the genesis of the K/T clastic rocks in central and western Cuba.
506 Importance in offshore hydrocarbon exploration]. In IV Convención Cubana de Ciencias de La
507 Tierra (Geociencias'2011).

508 Smit, J. (1982). Extinction and evolution of planktonic foraminifera after a major impact at the
509 Cretaceous/Tertiary boundary. *Geological Society of America Special Paper*, 190, 329–352.
510 <https://doi.org/10.1130/SPE190-p329>

511 Smit, J., & Romein, A. J. T. (1985). A sequence of events across the Cretaceous-Tertiary boundary.
512 Earth and Planetary Science Letters, 74(2–3), 155–170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/0012->
513 821X(85)90019-6

514 Tada, R., Iturralde-Vinent, M. A., Matsui, T., Tajika, E., Oji, T., Goto, K., Nakano, Y., Takayama,
515 H., Yamamoto, S., Kiyokawa, S., Toyoda, K., Garcia-Delgado, D., Diaz-Otero, C., & Rojas-
516 Consuegra, R. (2003). K/T boundary deposit in the proto-Caribbean basin. American
517 Association of Petroleum Geologists Memoir, 79, 582–604.

518 Tada, R., Nakano, Y., Iturralde-Vinent, M. A., Yamamoto, S., Kamata, T., Tajika, E., Toyoda, K.,
519 Kiyokawa, S., García-Delgado, D., Oji, T., Goto, K., Takayama, H., Rojas-Consuegra, R., &
520 Matsui, T. (2002). Complex tsunami waves suggested by the Cretaceous-Tertiary boundary
521 deposit at the Moncada section, western Cuba. In C. Koeberl & K. G. MacLeod (Eds.),
522 Catastrophic events and mass extinctions: Impacts and beyond (Vol. 356, pp. 109–123).
523 Geological Society of America Special Paper.

524 Takayama, H., Tada, R., Matsui, T., Iturralde-Vinent, M. A., Oji, T., Tajika, E., Kiyokawa, S.,
525 Garcia, D., Okada, H., Hasegawa, T., & Toyoda, K. (2000). Origin of the Peñalver Formation
526 in northwestern Cuba and its relation to K/T boundary impact event. Sedimentary Geology,
527 135(1–4), 295–320. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0037-0738\(00\)00087-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0037-0738(00)00087-7)

528 Thiadens, A. A. (1937). Geology of the southern part of the province Santa Clara (Las Villas)
529 Cuba. Ministerio de Energía y Minas, Oficina Nacional de Recursos Minerales.

530 Truitt, P., & Pardo, G. (1953). Placetas-Fomento Road Traverse. Ministerio de Energía y Minas,
531 Oficina Nacional de Recursos Minerales.

532 Villegas-Martín, J., & Rojas-Consuegra, R. (2011). Icnogénero Teredolites en megabloques del
533 límite Cretácico – Paleógeno (K/Pg), Formación Peñalver, Cuba occidental [Ichnogenus

534 Teredolites in megablocks of the Cretaceous-Paleogene (K/Pg) boundary, Peñalver Formation,
535 western Cuba]. *Revista Española de Paleontología*, 46(1), 45–52.

536 Wade, B. R., Pearson, P. N., Berggren, W. A., & Pälike, H. (2011). Review and revision of
537 Cenozoic tropical planktonic foraminiferal biostratigraphy and calibration to the geomagnetic
538 polarity and astronomical time scale. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 104(1–3), 111–142.
539 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2010.09.003>

540 Wassall, H. (1954). In P. Brönnimann & G. Pardo (1964). Annotations to the correlation chart and
541 catalogue of formations (Las Villas province). Geological Report 456. Ministerio de Energía y
542 Minas, Oficina Nacional de Recursos Minerales.

543 Yamamoto, S., Hasegawa, T., Tada, R., Goto, K., Rojas-Consuegra, R., Díaz-Otero, C., García-
544 Delgado, D. E., Yamamoto, S., Sakuma, H., & Matsui, T. (2010). Environmental and
545 vegetational changes recorded in sedimentary leaf wax n-alkanes across the Cretaceous–
546 Paleogene boundary at Loma Capiro, Central Cuba. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology,*
547 *Palaeoecology*, 295(1–2), 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2010.05.013>

548

549 **Figure Captions:**

550 Figure 1. Location map of the study area. A) General map of Cuba showing the main tectonic
551 terrains. B) Detailed map of central Cuba indicating the location of the Fomento section (red star)
552 in the province of Sancti Spíritus.

553 Figure 2. Geological setting of the K-Pg boundary section at Río Cangrejo (red asterisk), east of
554 the town of Fomento.

555 Figure 3. Regional stratigraphic column (based on Kantshev et al., 1978), highlighting the
556 Chicxulub impact ejecta-rich layer within the Cabaiguán piggy-back basin, central Cuba.

557 Figure 4. Lithostratigraphic column of the Río Cangrejo section in Fomento. Note the
558 sedimentological complexity of the Complex Clastic Unit (CCU) and the distinction of three
559 different intervals.

560 Figure 5. General view of the Complex Clastic Unit (CCU) at the Río Cangrejo section, Fomento,
561 Sancti Spíritus province. a) Sandy marl and reddish siltstone of the Isabel Formation at the base
562 of the CCU, and the lower subunit on the north wall; b) Lower and middle subunits of the CCU
563 on the south wall; c and d) Blocks, lithoclasts and bioclasts in the lower subunit, detail of the
564 south wall; e) Middle and upper subunits with marked cross-bedding, north wall; f) Contact
565 between the spherule-rich grey-green upper subunit and the purple siltstone of the Fomento
566 Formation, at the bottom of the excavated trench.

567 Figure 6. Photomicrographs of different ejecta elements in the CCU of the Río Cangrejo. a)
568 Bubble-bearing spherule with a calcite-filled vesicle; b) Spherule surrounded by limestone
569 fragments (left) and broken altered spherules (upper right); c) Basement fragment (quartz schist,
570 center) with quartz grains; d) Level with accretionary lapilli and rare shocked basement
571 fragments; e) Accretionary lapillus grain (center) with a fragment of silica-altered glass core
572 surrounded by a fine microsparitic matrix; f) The accretionary lapillus grain is surrounded by
573 quartz grains, bioclasts and carbonate lithics. The core has a teardrop shape confirming its origin
574 from a fluid melt. The outer rim of the lapillus is composed of darker fine-grained micrite. All
575 images are standard polished thin sections under cross-polarized light.

576 Figure 7. Scanning Electron Microscopy (EDS) images of CCU material and spherules. a) Detail
577 (image 004x100) of an isolated spherule composed of calcite and clay; b) Spherules (001x170)
578 of calcite with an outer clay ring; c) Calcite (008x110) with the presence of darker crystalline
579 phases, likely feldspar or zeolite; d) Calcite (008x120) with barium in zeolite, possibly
580 harmotome or phillipsite.

581 Figure 8. Stratigraphic distribution of planktic foraminiferal species across the K/Pg boundary in
582 the Fomento section. Biozones follow the planktic foraminiferal zonations of Arz and Molina
583 (2002) for the Maastrichtian and Wade et al. (2011) for the Danian. * Condensed level (clayey
584 carbonate hardground) containing mixed assemblages of the P α , P1a, P1b and P1c Biozones of
585 Wade et al. (2011).

586
587 Figure 1
588
589
590
591
592
593
594
595
596
597
598
599
600

601
602

Figure 2

603
604 Figure 3
605

606
607 Figure 4
608

609
610 Figure 5
611

612
613 Figure 6
614

004

001

008

008

615
616
617

Figure 7

